

Geomorphometric atlas of Antarctic periglacial territories: Structure, content, examples

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Abstract—We have started a project on creating the geomorphometric atlas of Antarctic periglacial territories. In this article, we briefly describe a structure and a content of the atlas being developed as well as present examples of geomorphometric modeling and mapping for three typical Antarctic periglacial territories, such as, the Cape Burks oasis (Marie Byrd Land, West Antarctica), the Haswell Island (Queen Mary Land, East Antarctica), and the Leningradsky Nunatak (Oates Land, East Antarctica). The atlas will concentrate on multi-scale, multi-aspect quantitative information on the topography of Antarctic ice-free territories, present it in a systematized, organized, and easy-to-read form as well as provide scientific and information support for fundamental and applied research in Antarctica. The atlas development is expected to be completed by 2030.

I. INTRODUCTION

Periglacial, or ice-free landscapes of Antarctica can be classified into the following three main types [1–3]:

1. Antarctic oases, that is, ice-free coastal, shelf, and mountainous areas. Coastal oases are located between the continental ice sheet and the ocean; shelf oases are situated between the continental ice sheet and ice shelves; and mountain ones can be found in intramountain valleys and depressions.
2. Ice-free islands (or their parts) situated outside the ice shelves.
3. Ice-free mountain ranges (or their portions) and nunataks.

In all types of periglacial landscapes of Antarctica, there are primitive soils and vegetation represented by mosses, algae, and lichens. A special feature of oases and ice-free islands are stream and lake systems, which exist during the austral summer.

Geomorphometric mapping of Antarctic periglacial landscapes is promising both for obtaining new knowledge about the quantitative characteristics of the topography of these unique territories, and for the further use of morphometric information for solving fundamental and applied problems of geosciences. For some ice-free Antarctic areas (i.e., Larsemann Hills, Thala Hills, Schirmacher Oasis, and Fildes Peninsula), we previously performed geomorphometric modeling and mapping [4, 5]. However, geomorphometric mapping of such territories needs to be posed on a larger scope and more comprehensively. It would be expedient to create a geomorphometric atlas of all periglacial territories of Antarctica [6]. The creation of such an atlas will allow generalizing and systematizing regional morphometric information in a form traditional for geosciences.

In this article, we briefly describe a structure and a content of the atlas being developed [6] as well as present examples of modeling and mapping for three typical Antarctic periglacial territories, such as, an oasis, an island, and a nunatak.

II. ATLAS STRUCTURE AND CONTENT

The atlas will include twenty regional chapters as follows: (1) Queen Maud Land, (2) Enderby Land, (3) Kemp Land, (4) MacRobertson Land, (5) Princess Elizabeth Land, (6) Wilhelm II Land, (7) Queen Mary Land, (8) Wilkes Land, (9) George V Land, (10) Oates Land, (11) Victoria Land, (12) Transantarctic Mountains, (13) Marie Byrd Land, (14) Ellsworth Land, (15) Alexander I Island, (16) Palmer Land, (17) Graham Land, (18) South Shetland Islands, (19) Queen Elizabeth Land, and (20) Coats Land.

Analyzing available topographic maps, satellite images, and other published data, we selected 191 completely or partially ice-

free Antarctic territories [6], which will be modeled, mapped, and presented in the atlas. All ice-free areas will be grouped within regional chapters.

For each periglacial territory, the atlas will contain the following maps and materials:

1. A series of morphometric maps. Among others, the following morphometric variables will be calculated and mapped: slope gradient (G), horizontal curvature (k_h), vertical curvature (k_v), minimum curvature (k_{min}), maximum curvature (k_{max}), catchment area (CA), topographic wetness index, stream power index (SI), and wind exposition index. For physical mathematical and physical geographical interpretations of these variables, see [7].

2. A series of thematic maps derived from morphometric ones. Among others, the following maps will be generated: landform classification, geological lineaments, etc.

3. Textual reference material (methodological explanations for maps, physical and geographical interpretations of morphometric maps, etc.).

The following scales and projections will be used in the atlas:

- 1 : 10,000,000 and the polar stereographic projection for one overview hill-shaded map of the Antarctic topography.
- 1 : 1,000,000 and Lambert conformal conic projection for one overview hill-shaded map for each chapter of the atlas (that is, for each Antarctic region).
- 1 : 100,000 / 1 : 50,000 / 1 : 25,000 and UTM projection for series of morphometric and thematic maps for each territory depending on the territory size and readability of the derived maps.

As input data for geomorphometric calculations and mapping, we use fragments of the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA) [8] with grid spacings of 2, 8, and 10 m. REMA is presented in the polar stereographic projection; elevations are given relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid. Before the calculation, we reproject REMA fragments into the UTM projection preserving the original grid spacings during interpolation.

For pre-processing and editing of the REMA fragments as well as geomorphometric calculations and mapping, we use the SAGA software.

III. EXAMPLES

Figs. 1–3 show morphometric maps for three typical periglacial areas of Antarctica.

Fig. 1 represents several morphometric maps for the Cape Burks oasis, the site of the Russkaya seasonal research base (Marie Byrd Land, West Antarctica; 74.75549°S, 136.81336°W).

Fig. 2 shows some morphometric maps of the Haswell Island (the ornithological Antarctic Specially Protected Area No. 127), located in the Davis Sea, about 2.5 km north of the Mabus Point, the site of the Mirny year-round polar station (Queen Mary Land, East Antarctica; 66.52567°S, 92.99541°E).

Fig. 3 describes morphology of the Leningradsky Nunatak, the site of the Leningradskaya seasonal research base, which belongs to the Holladay Nunataks cluster (Oates Land, East Antarctica; 69.50177°S, 159.3884°E).

Digital models of G and curvatures were derived from the non-smoothed REMA fragments by the author's finite-difference method [7], while models of CA and SI were computed using the maximum-gradient based multiple flow direction algorithm [9]. For the Cape Burks, Haswell Island, and Leningradsky Nunatak, grid spacings of the REMA fragments and morphometric models are 8 m, 2 m, and 2 m, respectively.

IV. DISCUSSION

As a large cartographic work, any atlas should have integrity, which is provided by the completeness and internal unity of the atlas content. The completeness of the geomorphometric atlas being developed is ensured by two factors:

1. The atlas will present the majority of ice-free areas of Antarctica.
2. For these territories, maps of all key, scientifically important and interpretable morphometric variables will be created.

The internal unity of the atlas is ensured by three factors:

1. A series of morphometric maps of each territory are created at the same scale that ensures ease of comparison of these maps.
2. A series of maps of one set of morphometric variables will be calculated for all territories that will facilitate a comparative analysis of the topography of different landscapes.
3. Each morphometric map quantitatively describes a certain property of the topography and has a unique physical mathematical as well as physical geographical interpretation. Morphometric maps of one series complement each other.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have started a project on creating the geomorphometric atlas of Antarctic periglacial territories. The atlas will concentrate multi-scale, multi-aspect quantitative information on the topography of Antarctic ice-free territories, present it in a systematized, organized, and easy-to-read form as well as provide scientific and information support for fundamental and applied research in Antarctica. The atlas development is expected to be completed by 2030.

Figure 1. Morphometric maps of the Cape Burks oasis and adjacent glacier: (a) elevation, (b) CA , (c) k_v , (d) k_h , (e) G , and (f) SI

Figure 2. Morphometric maps of the Haswell Island: (a) elevation, (b) CA , (c) k_v , (d) k_h , (e) k_{min} , and (f) k_{max}

Figure 3. Morphometric maps of the Leningradsky Nunatak and a surrounding glacier: (a) elevation, (b) CA , (c) k_h , (d) k_v , (e) k_{min} , and (f) k_{max}

REFERENCES

- [1] Markov, K.K., V.I. Bardin, V.L. Lebedev, A.I. Orlov, and I.A. Suetova, 1970. "The Geography of Antarctica", Israel Program for Scientific Translations, Jerusalem, 370 p.
- [2] Simonov, I.A., 1971. "Oases of East Antarctica", Hydrometeoizdat, Leningrad, 176 p. (in Russian).
- [3] Korotkevich, E.S., 1972. "Polar Deserts", Hydrometeoizdat, Leningrad, 419 p. (in Russian).
- [4] Florinsky, I.V., 2023. "Geomorphometric modeling and mapping of Antarctic oases." arXiv Preprints, 2305.07523.
- [5] Florinsky, I.V., 2023. "Larsemann Hills: Geomorphometric modeling and mapping." Polar Science, 38, 100969.
- [6] Florinsky, I.V., 2024. "A project of a geomorphometric atlas of ice-free Antarctic territories." InterCarto. InterGIS, 30(2), 53–79 (in Russian).
- [7] Florinsky, I.V., 2025. "Digital Terrain Analysis", 3rd rev. enl. ed. Academic Press, London, 455 p.
- [8] Howat, I.M., C. Porter, B.E. Smith, M.-J. Noh, and P. Morin, 2019. "The Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica." Cryosphere, 13, 665–674.
- [9] Qin, C., A.-X. Zhu, T. Pei, B. Li, C. Zhou, and L. Yang, 2007. "An adaptive approach to selecting a flow-partition exponent for a multiple-flow-direction algorithm." International Journal of Geographical Information Science, 21, 443–458.